

Mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with histidine and biguanide

Tannistha Roy Barman and G. N. Mukherjee*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta,
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : mukherg@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-033-2351-9755/2241-3222

Manuscript received 11 January 2010, revised 24 February 2010, accepted 25 February 2010

Abstract : Combined spectrophotometric and computer-based pH-metric investigations on the mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with histidine [(C₃H₃N₂)CH₂CH(NH₂)COOH, hisH[±]] and biguanide [NH₂C(=NH)NHC(=NH)NH₂, Bg] in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength (*I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³) and 25 ± 1°C. provided evidence of binary [Cu(hism)⁺], [Cu(hism-H)], [Cu(hism)₂], [Cu(hism)(hism-H)⁻], [Cu(hism-H)₂²⁻] and [Cu(Bg)²⁺] and ternary [Cu(hism)(Bg)⁺], [Cu(hism-H)(Bg)], [Cu(Bg)(OH)⁺] and [Cu(Bg-H)(OH)] complexes. Histidine provides both *histamine-like* [(NH₂, N-imidazole i.e. (hism⁻)] and mixed *histamine-like glycine-like* [(NH₂, N-imidazole) (NH₂, COO⁻) i.e. (hism⁻)(gly⁻)] chelation, barring simple *glycine-like* (gly⁻) chelation. Binding affinity of Cu^{II} for (NH₂, =NH) bidentate chelating biguanide is so strong that the histidine-imidazole deprotonated mixed-ligand complex, [Cu(hism-H)(Bg)] decomposes at pH > 10 to biguanide (=NH) deprotonated ternary hydroxo complex, [Cu(Bg-H)(OH)], setting free the his⁻ ligand ion in solution, a phenomenon of great biological significance, in regard to medicinal applications of the title ligands and their metal derivatives.

Keywords : Copper, histidine, biguanide, mixed-ligand complex equilibria.

Introduction

In majority of copper proteins, copper atoms are coordinated by one or more imidazole-N atoms of histidine residues of the protein chains^{1,2}. Histidine, on the other hand, shows ambidentism in its modes of coordination to copper³⁻⁵. Depending upon the pH and molar proportions of the metal to ligand in the solution, histidine (Scheme 1) may coordinate Cu^{II} ion in three different modes :

(a) as a (N, N) bidentate *histamine-like* ligand (hism⁻), using the amino-N and imidazole-N atoms,

(b) as a (N, O⁻) bidentate *glycine-like* ligand (gly⁻), using the amino-N and carboxylate-O atoms, and

(c) as a (N, N, O⁻) tridentate *histidine-like* ligand (his⁻), using the amino-N, imidazole-N and carboxylate-O atoms. Two of these three donor atoms coordinate two equatorial positions on the copper coordination geometry and the third donor atom coordinates from an apical position.

Equilibrium and structural studies on 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : histidine complexes formed at different pH indicated varieties of modes of coordination of histidine to copper in these complexes, viz. [Cu (a)₂], [Cu (a)(b)] and [Cu (a)(c)]

with the exclusion of [Cu (b)₂]⁶⁻¹⁰. These opened the scope for further investigation in this area.

Due to imidazole-N coordination, histidine, among all the natural amino acids, shows highest affinity for Cu^{II} (log β₂ ~ 18.3)³ and histidine bonded Cu^{II} can discriminate between σ-basic and π-acidic ligands in ternary complexes¹¹. With a view to elucidate the modes of coordination of histidine (hisH[±]) to Cu^{II} in presence of strongly coordinating [(N, N)] bidentate ligand, biguanide [H₂¹N-C(=NH)²NH³NH⁴C(=NH)⁵NH₂, Bg] (Scheme 1), mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with histidine and Bg have been investigated by combined pH-metric (Fig. 1) and spectrophotometric (Fig. 2) measurements in aqueous solution at 25 ± 1°C at a fixed ionic strength, *I* = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃). Formation constants of the most probable complexes have been evaluated and the complex formation equilibria have been elucidated by mathematical modeling¹² of the pH-titration data and analysis of the speciation curves.

Biguanide itself, its N-substituted derivatives and their metal complexes have recently shown anti diabetic, anti malarial properties and effectiveness in reduction of anxiety, pain and memory disorders^{13,14}. Histidine and some of its metal derivatives have been identified as Alzheimer's

Scheme 1

A β -channel blockers, preventing A β -cytotoxicity¹⁵. In this context, the results of the present equilibrium study are very likely to provide useful clues for elucidation molecular mechanism of drug actions of these compounds.

Results and discussion

(a) Calculation of formation constants :

The overall formation constant (β_{pqrs}) of a homo metallic generalized ternary complex species, $[Cu_p(his)_q(Bg)_r(OH)_s]$ (Table 1) may be defined according to¹²,

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[Cu_p (his)_q (Bg)_r (OH)_s]}{[Cu]^p [his]^q [Bg]^r [OH]^s} \quad (1a)$$

The stoichiometric members, p , q and r may be positive or zero, s is a negative integer for a protonated species such as H_2hisH^{2+} , $(H_2his^\pm)^+$, H_2Bg^{2+} , HBg^+ , etc., positive integer for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species like $Cu(OH)^+$, $Cu(Bg-H)^+$, $Cu(his-H)$ and zero for a normal species such as his^- , Bg , $Cu(Bg)^{2+}$, $Cu(Gu)^+$, $Cu(his)^+$, $Cu(his)(Bg)^+$ etc. For 1 : 1 and 1 : 5 binary Cu^{II} : ligand systems, $p = 1$ and the value of q and r depend upon the molar ratios of metal : ligand in the complexes supposed to be formed in the solution. For 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : his : Bg system, however, $p = q = r = 1$. Since the pH range of some of the complex formation equilibria are overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of Cu^{II} (aq) ion, occurrence of binary as well as ternary hydroxo complex species are also considered in calculating the formation constants (β_{pqrs}) of the metal-ligand complexes, however, pH-titration data (Fig. 1) only prior to the commencement of any turbidity are subjected to calculation.

Bidentate ($NH_2, =NH$) mode of chelation by biguanide is well known^{16,17}. For the histidine ligand (his^-), bidentate

Fig. 1. Representative pH titration curves of Cu^{II} : biguanide : histidine system : ($M = mol\ dm^{-3}$) : 1, 0.005 (M) HNO_3 ; 2, (1) + 0.001 (M) H_2Bg^{2+} ; 3, (1) + 0.001 (M) H_2hisH^{2+} ; 4, (2) + 0.001 (M) Cu^{II} ; 5, (3) + 0.001 (M) Cu^{II} ; 6, (5) + 0.001 (M) H_2Bg^{2+} ; initial volume = 0.025 dm^3 , titrant = 0.1 (M) $NaOH$, ionic strength, $I = 0.1$ (M) $NaNO_3$.

($NH_2, N-imz$) i.e., histamine-like ($hism^-$, mode-a) and (NH_2, COO^-), i.e., glycine-like (gly^- , mode-b) chelation along with mixed histamine-like glycine-like chelation are considered, but inclusion of complexes with only glycine-like chelation gives larger values of standard deviations. Consequently, such species are excluded from the calculation. The modes of coordination of the ligands are established from the shifts of electronic spectral absorption maximum¹⁸ of Cu^{II} in the binary and ternary metal-ligand mixtures (Figs. 2) with change of pH. Complex formation equilibria are elucidated by analyzing the speciation curves (Figs. 3 and 4), obtained as computer out put.

(b) Proton-ligand equilibria :

(i) Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of histidine :

In dilute acidic solution ($pH \leq 2$), histidine ($hisH^\pm$) exists in its di-protonated (H_2hisH^\pm)²⁺ form, in which the added protons remain associated with the imidazole- N^3 atom and the amino-N atom (Scheme 2).

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of (a) 1:1 Cu^{II} histidine, (b) 1:5 Cu^{II} histidine, (c) 1:1:1 Cu^{II} histidine biguanide systems at different pH. Ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO₃)

The carboxylic acid group remains partly ionized ($\text{pK}_3 \sim 1.60$). Above $\text{pH} \sim 3$, the zwitterionic (H_2his^\pm)⁺ is the dominant species (Fig. 3). The imidazolium ($^3\text{NH}^+$) proton is lost above $\text{pH} 5$ ($\text{pK}_2 \sim 6.02$) and the aminium proton ($-\text{NH}_3^+$) is lost above $\text{pH} 8$ ($\text{pK}_1 \sim 9.10$). Due to tautomerism within the imidazole ring, the ¹NH hydrogen atom in Hhis^\pm and his^- ions may alternate between ¹N and ³N atoms¹⁸.

(ii) Protonation-deprotonation of biguanide :

In dilute acidic solution ($\text{pH} \leq 2$) biguanide (Bg) exists as its dicationic form (H_2Bg^{2+}). The added protons remain bound to the $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{NH}_2$ groups^{17a,c} (Scheme 1). These protonated forms disappear with rise of pH, giving two well separated buffer regions ($2 < \text{pH} < 4$

and ($9.5 < \text{pH} < 11.5$). Due to structural symmetry of biguanide, it is not possible to specify which group among $-\text{NH}_3^+$ and $-\text{NH}_3^+$ deprotonates at which buffer region.

(c) Binary systems

Stoichiometry of the binary Cu^{II} histidine, Cu^{II} biguanide and ternary Cu^{II} histidine biguanide complexes are presented in Table 1 along with refined values of their formation constants.

(i) 1:1 Cu^{II} histidine equilibria

Complex formation of Cu^{II} with histidine in the 1:1 binary system starts at $\sim \text{pH} 3$, at which the ligand exists mostly in its $[\text{H}_2\text{his}^\pm]^+$ form (Scheme 2) and the metal-hydroxo species, viz. $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ are totally absent (Fig. 3a). 1:1 Cu^{II} histidine complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})^+]$ (8), (Table 1), with a concentration maxima ($\sim 80\%$) at $\text{pH} \sim 5.5$, is the major copper containing species in the pH range 3–8.

Table 1. Stoichiometry of the Cu^{II} histidine-biguanide complexes and refined values of the proton ligand and metal ligand constants

Sl no	Complex species	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	$\log \beta_{pqrs}$
	$[\text{Cu}_p(\text{his})_q(\text{Bg})_r(\text{OH})_s]$					
1	$[\text{H}_2\text{hisH}]^{2+}$	0	1	0	-3	16.72
2	$[\text{H}_2\text{his}^\pm]^+$	0	1	0	-2	15.12
3	$[\text{Hhis}^\pm]$	0	0	1	-1	9.10
4	H_2Bg^{2+}	0	0	1	-2	14.20
5	HBg^+	0	0	1	-1	10.90
6	$[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+]$	1	0	0	1	-6.29
7	$[\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2]$	1	0	0	2	-13.05
8	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})^+]$	1	1	0	0	10.21
9	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism-H})]$	1	1	0	1	4.18
10	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})_2]$	1	2	0	0	20.28
11	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})(\text{gly})]$	1	2	0	0	19.80
12	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})(\text{hism-H})^-]$	1	2	0	1	13.00
13	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism-H})_2^{2-}]$	1	2	0	2	4.95
14	$[\text{Cu}(\text{Bg})^{2+}]$	1	0	1	0	6.74
15	$[\text{Cu}(\text{Bg})(\text{OH})^+]$	1	0	1	1	1.70
16	$[\text{Cu}(\text{Bg-H})(\text{OH})]$	1	0	1	2	-5.18
17	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})(\text{Bg})^+]$	1	1	1	0	18.22
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}(17)$					(+) 1.27
18	$[\text{Cu}(\text{hism})(\text{Bg})(-\text{H})]$	1	1	1	1	9.95

hism⁻ histamine-like (NH_2 , N-imz) coordination by histidine
gly⁻ glycine-like (NH_2 , $-\text{COO}^-$) coordination by histidine

As the speciation curves (Figs. 3a) imply, formation of the complex (8) may be described according to the

Scheme 2

eqm. (2) :

Two possible modes of bidentate chelation by the his⁻ ligand ion, viz. *histamine-like* coordination (*hism*⁻) using the amino-N atom and the imidazole-N atom (mode-*a*) and *glycine-like* coordination (*gly*⁻) using the amino N-

atom and the carboxylate-O atom (mode-*b*) give two structural possibilities, (8a) and (8b) respectively for the complex (8). Cu^{II} in both these isomeric structures tends to take up two molecules of solvent H₂O to achieve its preferred 4-coordinated square planar geometry, i.e., [Cu(NH₂)(N-imz)(H₂O)₂] (8a) and or [Cu(NH₂)(COO⁻)(H₂O)₂] (8b) (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Electronic spectral absorption maxima (λ_{\max}) of Cu^{II} corresponding these two square planar structures may be estimated with the aid of the eqs. (3a) and (3b) respectively^{17,18} :

$$\lambda_{\max} \text{ (nm)} = 10^3 / [0.294 (C=O/H_2O/OH^-/NH) + 0.346 (COO^-) + 0.434 (N\text{-imz}) + 0.46 (NH_2) + 0.494 (=N^-)] \quad (3a)$$

$$\lambda_{\max} \text{ (nm)} = 10^3 / [0.301 (C=O/H_2O/OH^-/NH) + 0.342 (COO^-) + 0.453 (NH_2) + 0.485 (N^{\cdot}C=O)] \quad (3b)$$

where, the groups in the parentheses represent the number of such coordinating groups (total not exceeding 4) and the numerical coefficients are their ligand field contributions in μm^{-1} . Estimated λ_{\max} values for the structures (8a) and (8b) are 675 nm and 733 nm respectively. The experimental λ_{\max} value (693 nm) of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine mixture at pH ~ 5–5.5, at which the complex (8) passes through a concentration maximum (Fig. 3a), is closer to the estimated λ_{\max} value corresponding to structure (8a). Slightly higher experimental λ_{\max} value (by ~ 18 nm) suggests apical carboxylate coordination of intermolecular nature. The alternative structure (8b) with *glycine-like* chelation may be discarded, because of wide difference of the estimated λ_{\max} corresponding to this structure from the experimental λ_{\max} value.

Another buffer region corresponding to the release of one mole of H⁺ per mole of Cu^{II} is observed between pH 6–8 with a blue shift of the λ_{\max} (~by ≥ 20 nm) to 656 nm around pH 6.5–7 (Fig. 2). This buffer region can not be due to deprotonation of a coordinated H₂O molecule to OH⁻ ion within the complex (8, i.e. 8a), since H₂O and OH⁻ are very closely placed in the spectrochemical series. The only possible source of this buffer action is release of the imidazole (¹NH \rightleftharpoons ³NH) proton from (8a), producing [Cu(hism-H)] (9) (Scheme 3), according to the eqm. (4) :

The pK^H (8) value (~6.03) corresponding to the deprotonation (eqm. 4) :

$$\text{pK}^{\text{H}} (8) = \log \beta_{1101} - \log \beta_{1100} \quad (4a)$$

reflects the enhancement of acidity of otherwise neutral histidine-imidazole ring ¹NH due to coordination of the tertiary ³N-atom to Cu^{II}. Ligand field contribution (eq. 3a) of deprotonated imidazole moiety of histidine to Cu^{II}

comes around ~0.48 μm^{-1} and ~0.52 μm^{-1} respectively in the presence and in the absence of apical carboxylate coordination.

(ii) 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine equilibria :

Complex formation in 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine system starts around pH 2.5 (Fig. 3b) with appearance of the 1 : 1 complex (8) (eqm. 2), which passes through a concentration maximum (~30%) at pH ~ 3.5–4, where the imidazole deprotonated 1 : 1 complex (9) does not occur at all. The major Cu^{II} containing species above pH 4, however, is the 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : histidine complex, which may exist in two isomeric structures, viz. [Cu(hism)₂] (10), involving *histamine-histamine-like* (mode-*a*) coordination by the two his⁻ ligands and Cu(hism)(gly) (11) involving *mixed-histamine-like glycine-like* coordination (modes-*a, b*) by the two his⁻ ligands (Scheme 4).

The uncoordinated carboxylate-O atoms and imidazole-N atoms in structures (10) and (11), however, can provide intermolecular apical coordination to Cu^{II}. Inclusion of structures involving only *glycine-like* chelation (mode-*b*) viz. Cu(gly)⁺ and Cu(gly)₂, gives higher values of standard deviations, therefore, such species are not considered. The speciation curves (Fig. 3b) of this system shows the coexistence of almost equal % of Cu²⁺(aq) ion, the 1 : 1 complex [Cu(hism)(H₂O)₂⁺] (8a) and two forms of the 1 : 2 complex, viz. [Cu(hism)₂] (10) and [Cu(hism)(gly)] (11), around pH ~ 3.5–4. The estimated average of the λ_{\max} value (*ca.* 662 nm) of these species is close to the experimental λ_{\max} value (654 nm) of 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine mixture at pH (~4) (Fig. 2b). A small blue shift of (~27 nm) to 617 nm, with rise of pH to 5, suggests transformation of (11) to (10) in increasing proportions. Since all these three complex species, (8a), (10) and (11) occur simultaneously in the complex formation equilibria, the initial stages of complex formation in 1 : 5 Cu^{II} : histidine system may be described according to eqm. (2) followed by eqm. (5) and (6) as the speciation curves (Fig. 3b) imply :

A red shift of the λ_{\max} value to 636–642 nm with rise of pH (above 6) is indicative of apical coordination of Cu^{II} by carboxylate-O atom and or uncoordinated imidazole-N atom in the complexes (10) and (11), which pass through their respective concentration maxima (~55–60%) and (40–45%) around pH 5.5–6. Above pH 6, both (10) and (11) disappear simultaneously with building up of

Scheme 4

concentration of the imidazole deprotonated complexes, [Cu(hism)(hism-H)⁻] (12) and [Cu(hism-H)₂²⁻] (13). Finally above pH 8, (12) is transformed to (13) (Scheme 5).

Although small, but a definite final blue shift of the λ_{max} value by ~5–6 nm is observed above pH 9 (Fig. 2b), as increasing proportions of (12) and (13) appear in the solution through deprotonation of coordinated imidazole in (10) and (11) (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

(iii) 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : biguanide equilibria :

Complex formation in the 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : biguanide system starts around pH ~5, at which the metal ion exists as [Cu²⁺ (aq)], [Cu(OH)⁺ (aq)] (6) and [Cu(Bg)(OH)⁺ (aq)] (15) and the ligand exists in its mono protonated (HBg⁺) form. Two moles of H⁺ per mole of Cu^{II} are released in the pH range 5 ~ 6.5, at which the ternary hydroxo complex (15) appears to be the dominant copper containing species. The Bg ligand in this complex provides (N, N) bidentate chelation to Cu^{II} using its (¹NH₂, =⁴NH) or

(=²NH, ⁵NH₂) groups^{17a}. Above pH 7, the complex (15) undergoes deprotonation (pK^H ~ 6.88) from its coordinated =²NH, (or =⁴NH) group to produce [Cu(Bg-H)(OH)] (16) (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6

(d) 1 : 1 : 1 Ternary Cu^{II} : histidine : biguanide system :

Complex formation in the ternary 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine : biguanide system starts above pH 3 with appearance of the 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine complex [Cu(hism)(H₂O)₂⁺] (8a) (eqm. 2), which passes through its concentration maximum (~70%) around pH 5, at which small amounts (~8–10% each) of free Cu^{II} (aq) ion, the imidazole deprotonated 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine complex, [Cu(hism-H)] (9) (eqm. 4) and the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex, [Cu(hism)(Bg)⁺] (17) occur (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Speciation curves of (a) 1 1 and (b) 1 5 Cu^{II} histidine systems 1, $\text{H}_2\text{hisH}^{2+}$, 2, $(\text{H}_2\text{his}^\pm)^+$, 3, Hhis^\pm 6 $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, 7 $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, 8, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})^+$, 9, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m}-\text{H})$, 10, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})_2$, 11, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})(\text{gly})$, 12, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})(\text{his}^\text{m}-\text{H})$ 13 $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m} \text{H}_2)^2$ FM = Free Cu^{II} , FB1 = Free his^-

Fig. 4 Speciation curves of 1 1 1 Cu^{II} histidine biguanide system 1, $\text{H}_2\text{hisH}^{2+}$, 2, $(\text{H}_2\text{his}^\pm)^+$, 3, Hhis^\pm , 4 H_2Bg^{2+} 5 HB_b , 6, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$, 7, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$, 8, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})^+$, 9, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m}-\text{H})$, 14, $\text{Cu}(\text{Bg})^{2+}$, 15, $\text{Cu}(\text{Bg})(\text{OH})^+$, 16, $\text{Cu}(\text{Bg}-\text{H})(\text{OH})$, 17, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})(\text{Bg})^+$, 18, $\text{Cu}(\text{his}^\text{m})(\text{Bg})(-\text{H})$, FM = Free Cu^{II} , FB1 = Free his^- , FB2 = Free Bg^-

Concentration of (8a) declines above pH 5 with rise in the proportions of the complexes (9) according to eqm. (4) and of (17) according to eqm. (7),

Both (9) and (17) dominate in the pH range 6–9, and pass through their respective concentration maxima ~55% and ~40% around pH 7.5 i.e. pH of biological relevance. At still higher pH (7.5–10) the ternary complex (17) disappears with appearance of complex (18) through release of one mole of H^+ per mole of Cu^{II} , either from the coordinated ^2NH (or ^4NH) group of the Bg ligand producing (18a) or from the imidazole (NH) of the coordinated histidine ligand, producing (18b) or from both (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

Electronic spectral absorption maximum ($\lambda_{\text{max}} \sim 660$ nm) of 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine : biguanide mixture at pH 4.5–5 (Fig. 2c) at which 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : histidine complex (8a) makes ~75% of total Cu^{II} , is close to the estimated λ_{max} (~674 nm) corresponding a square planar $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_2)(\text{N}-\text{imz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ geometry of this complex (Scheme 3). With rise of pH up to 7.5, at which the complexes (9) and (17) make ~95% of total Cu^{II} , the λ_{max} value of the ternary mixture is blue shifted to ~627 nm, which is quite close to the estimated average λ_{max} (~630 nm), corresponding to square planar structures, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_2)(\text{N}^--\text{imz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (9) (654 nm) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_2)(\text{N}-\text{imz})(\text{NH}_2)(=\text{NH})]$ (17) (607 nm) of these complexes (Schemes 3 and 7). On further rise of pH (pH ~10), at which the deprotonated mixed ligand complex (18) makes ~80% of total Cu^{II} , λ_{max} value of the 1 : 1 : 1 mixture shows another blue shift to 606 nm, which is close to the estimated λ_{max} value (590 nm) corresponding to structure (18a) than the estimated λ_{max} value (541 nm) corresponding to structure (18b) (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8

Thus, it appears that, deprotonation of the ternary complex (17) involves release of the proton from the imidazole NH of the (NH₂, N-imz) coordinated histidine ligand (Scheme 7), but not from the coordinated ²NH (or ⁴NH) group of the biguanide ligand. Slightly higher value of experimental λ_{max} suggests intermolecular apical coordination of Cu^{II} by the carboxylate-O atom and or by the uncoordinated imidazole-N atom of the histidine ligand.

At very high pH (>10), the mixed ligand complex (18, i.e. 18a) disappears with simultaneous building up of concentration of the biguanide deprotonated ternary hydroxo complex, [Cu(Bg-H)(OH)(H₂O)] (16) suggesting decomposition of (18a), setting free the his⁻ ion, according to,

This last equilibrium (8) reveals stronger binding affinity of Cu^{II} for the biguanide anion, (Bg-H)⁻, over the imidazole NH deprotonated bidentate (NH₂, N⁻-imz) dianion, (hism-H)²⁻, a phenomenon of great biological significance, which is relevant to the medicinal actions of the title ligands and their metal complexes.

Experimental

All the reagents were of AR grades and their solutions were prepared in double distilled CO₂ free water. Procedures for standardization of the reagents, pH-metric and spectrophotometric measurements, evaluation of the equilibrium constants using the computer program SCOGS¹² were similar to those described in earlier communications^{17a,b,c} from this laboratory. For the determination of proton-ligand and metal-ligand complex formation constants, a series of solutions, each of initial volume 0.025 dm³, containing known amounts (0.005 mol dm⁻³) of free HNO₃, known amounts (0.001–0.0002 mol dm⁻³) of ligands, viz. histidine and biguanide in their protonated forms (H₂hisH[±])²⁺ and (H₂Bg²⁺) respectively, in the absence and in the presence of known amounts (0.0002–0.001 mol dm⁻³) of Cu^{II} nitrate were pH-metrically titrated with a carbonate free standard 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution, maintaining a fixed ionic strength, I = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃) at 25 ± 1°C (thermostated). Representa-

tive pH titration curves are presented in Fig. 1. Electronic spectral measurements of the binary and ternary metal-ligand mixtures were carried out after adjusting their pH values to the concentration maxima of different complexes.

References

1. P. C. Wilkins and R. G. Wilkins, in "Inorganic Chemistry in Biology", Oxford Scientific Publishing, Oxford, 1997.
2. H. Sigel and B. D. McCormick, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **89**, 2041.
3. K. M. Wellman, S. Bogdansky, C. Piontek C. R. Hare and M. Mathiesson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 25.
4. L. Casella and M. Gullotti, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 1983, **18**, 19.
5. Flora Carvera, Enrique Sanchez Macros, Patrick J. Merklng, Jesus Chabou and Adele Munoz-Paez, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 6674.
6. B. Evertsson, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1969, **B25**, 30.
7. T. Ono, H. Shimanouchi, Y. Sasada, T. Sakurai, O. Yamaguchi and A. Nakahara, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, **52**, 2229.
8. M. Ramonelli and R. Basosi, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1988, **143**, 404.
9. R. Grommen, P. Manikandan, Y. Gao, T. Shane, J. J. Shane, R. A. Schonheydt, B. M. Weckhuysen and D. Goldfarb, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 11488.
10. P. Manikandan, B. Epel and G. Goldfarb, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2001, **40**, 781.
11. H. Sigel, *Angew Chem., Internat Edit.*, 1975, **14**, 394.
12. I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397; I. G. Sayce, *Talanta*, 1970, **18**, 653; I. G. Sayce and V. S. Sharma, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 831.
13. T. N. Pirizol, R. Sibrun and C. Guran, *J. Env. Protection and Ecology*, 2005, **6**, 827.
14. A. K. Kesarwani, M. Chawla, R. S. Raghubanshi and A. Rampal, Ranbaxy Laboratories Limited (India), *PCT, Int. Appl.*, 2005, 28.
15. Neslon J. Arispe, Juan C. Diaz and Michael Flora, *Biophys. J. BioFAST*, 2008, **108**, 1355 17 (VI).
16. P. Ray, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **61**, 313 and references there in.
17. T. Roy Barman and G. N. Mukherjee, (a) *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2006, **118**, 411; (b) 2008, **120**, 377; (c) *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2009, **48**, 38; (d) *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 1018.
18. H. Sigel and R. B. Martin, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 385.

